

Pluralistic Memories Project

Methodological Report
Main survey – Palestine

Mai Albzour, Walid Iadadwa & Sandra Penić

1. Sampling strategy

The Pluralistic Memories Project (PMP) survey included a multi-stage stratified probability sample with unequal selection probabilities. The territory of West Bank and Jerusalem is administratively divided in 510 localities at the time of survey (Palestinian Central Bureau of Statistics(PCBS): http://www.pcbs.gov.ps/site/lang__en/803/default.aspx).

The PMP survey had the target sample of 1,000 respondents who are permanent adult Palestinian residents. The sampling was conducted in four stages:

- *Stage 1*: Selection of localities (target 50 localities with 20 respondents in each);
- *Stage 2*: Selection of two clusters (population locations) per locality (target 100 population locations);
- *Stage 3*: Selection of households from the population locations (10 households per population location/20 households per locality);
- *Stage 4*: Selection of a respondent among the eligible household members.

1.1. Selecting localities

In *Stage 1*, localities were randomly selected with the following procedure. The goal was to optimize the final sample based on three criteria: (1) *proximity to settlements* (the goal was to oversample localities (choose more localities) closer to the Israeli settlements), (2) whether the locality is a *camp* (the goal was to oversample camp localities), and (3) whether the locality belongs to *Jerusalem* (J1) (more localities were chosen from Jerusalem area). All localities were classified in one of four strata (1. Close to settlements, 2. Camp, 3. Jerusalem, 4. All other localities), and 50 target localities were selected with the probability proportional to size (PPS) within the strata (10 target localities were selected within each of the first three strata, and 20 target localities within the fourth strata). Due to the PPS procedure, the final selection consisted of 49 localities (as one locality was selected twice, and its sample size was doubled).

1.2. Selecting clusters, households and respondents

In *Stage 2*, each locality is split in a variable number of same size clusters (i.e., population locations), where each cluster contains approximately 1,000 individuals (estimated based on

the locality population size). The clusters are drawn following the main roads in a locality based on the updated maps. The next *Stage 3* consists of the selection of households. It is estimated that each cluster includes about 200 households (based on the assumption that an average household has 5 members). The households are selected with a random walk technique. Finally, in *Stage 4*, a respondent is randomly selected with a Kish table among all eligible household members (who are older than 18 and regularly live in the household).

1.3. Poststratification weights

Two poststratification weighting variables have been added into the database. The purpose of these variables is to compensate for unequal probability of selection of respondents. Whenever the aim of an analysis is to compute estimates which are relevant at the population level, the data need to be weighted by one of these variables.

The weights have been computed in order to correct for different selection probabilities within survey strata and households. First, Strata Weights 1 have been computed in the following way: Population strata weights (“Pop_w1_strata”) have been computed by dividing the population size in each stratum by the final sample size in each stratum. Design strata weights (“Des_w1_strata”) have been computed by multiplying the population weights with the final sample size and divided by the overall population size. Next, Household Weights 2 have been computed in the following way: Household weights (“Household_w2”) have been computed by dividing 1 with the number of eligible household members. Design household weights (“Des_w2_household”) have been computed by multiplying the household weights with the final sample size and divided by the sum of household weights. Finally, the combined Total weights have been computed in the following way: Total design weights (“des_weight”) have been computed by multiplying Design strata weights (“Des_w1_strata”) and Design household weights (“Des_w2_household”). Total population weights (“pop_weight”) have been computed by multiplying Total design weights (“des_weight”) with the final sample size and dividing by the total population size.

Total population weights should be used whenever the goal is to extrapolate the absolute numbers on the level of populations; in all other cases when using weights for inferential purposes, the total design weights should be used.

2. Survey questionnaire

The survey questionnaire included questions on respondent life events, personal information, social networks, short vignettes on memories of conflict, living conditions, community life, social identity, political attitudes and collective action.

2.1. Translation

The local PMP survey project team contracted a translator specialized in the academic field. The questionnaire, calendar, contact sheet, cards and network matrix were sent on September 9, 2017. They were translated into Arabic and delivered to the local team on the 30th September. During the translation process, the translator was in contact with the members of the local team, in order to discuss specific meanings and phrases to get an appropriate translation. The translation was carefully examined by Mai Albzour (PMP doctoral student) and then the problematic points were discussed with Prof. Randa Nasser (PMP coordinator).

Great effort and time were spent between the local team and the team in Lausanne in order to reach linguistic expressions that respond to the purposes of the questions in English. A further effort has been taken to contextualize the questionnaire, making it more appropriate for the local context. This included reformulating certain question to make them more appropriate for the Palestinian culture, as well as excluding potentially too sensitive questions to encourage participants' engagement in research. In this respect, the previous PMP pilot survey has been instructive, because most of the questions were previously discussed, and what was required in the main survey is to develop new items, improve the previous ones and their translation. For example, in the item A4.8 "Has a member of your immediate family been killed for political reasons?", the word "killed" has been translated into the word "martyr" to avoid disturbing the respondents. The most difficulties occurred in the translation of the questions on social identities (section C, in particular C4, C5 and C9), and conflict memories (section E, questions following vignettes) due to their complexity. Consequently, the items were simplified and translation corrected by the local team.

2.2. Development of questions and difficult items

On 10 July 2017, the Swiss team sent the initial questionnaire to discuss the existing items (previously tested in the pilot survey) and plan the development of new items in partnership with the local team. In particular, the items on political participation (the last items in section E and all the items in section F) were largely developed in this stage, in a collaborative process between the two teams. Mai Albzour led the development of questions on intergroup contact and normalization, collective action and political solutions of the conflict, as an original contribution within her PhD thesis work.

In a collaborative process, a number of initial items have been changed to be better adapted to the local cultural and political context. For instance, some changes were made in the life calendar (items on political violence) based on the local team's feedback. The previous instructions that asked the respondents to think about violence due to the occupation and internal political conflict were not appropriate for the item on internal violence. Hence, the local team suggested to ask directly whether the respondent was imprisoned by the PA in separate item from the calendar A4.13, and this suggestion was implemented. Another example are the items about collective action (in section on political participation), where the teams had lengthy discussion whether to directly ask the participants about their previous participation and future intentions. At the end, it was decided that this may be too sensitive, and the items were reformulated to ask about participation in more indirect way.

3. Fieldwork

3.1. Fieldwork network

The fieldwork across all areas of the West Bank and Jerusalem was conducted by three field teams, working together in a network coordinated by Walid Iadadwa and Jusour company from Ramallah. Part of the tasks were centralized and directly carried out in the Jusour headquarter:

- the preparation and printing of all the sampling, fieldwork and training materials, in particular the complete interviewer sets;
- all data entry and coding;
- overall supervision of fieldwork activities and regular reporting of progress and difficulties;
- archiving of all completed questionnaires for five years;

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- hiring of interviewers and regional coordinators;
- fieldwork logistics;
- back-checks (control of completed interviews).

Team composition

The overall fieldwork staff thus consisted of one overall project manager, three additional field team coordinators, as well as 7 supervisor, and 27 interviewers. The team worked in close collaboration with the local PMP researchers, Mai Albzour and Prof. Randa Nasser.

All interviewers had experience in the fieldwork and have previously worked in similar studies. The teams of 2 to 4 interviewers were supervised by the field supervisors (regional coordinators), who had the following role:

- Ensuring that interviewers reach the sampled localities and follow the correct procedure in selecting the households and respondents;
- Ensuring that interviewers have all needed material and use the correct formats;
- Reviewing the collected data and guiding researchers in case of problems;
- Collecting the completed questionnaires and delivering them to the central coordinator.

Fieldwork project manager

The project manager Walid Iadadwa was involved in the development of the sampling procedures, and has directly supervised the fieldwork and interviewer training. He personally provided training for coordinators and part of each field team's interviewers, in the local agencies' headquarters. Furthermore, together with the field team coordinators, he defined the local strategies for implementing the standardized sampling instructions and guidelines. During the fieldwork, he regularly informed the PMP team about the survey progress. When difficulties came up, he acted as a mediator between the logistical and practical concerns stemming from the field teams, on the one hand, and our methodological requirements, on the other.

3.2. Fieldwork timeline

After the initial training of the interviewers, test interviews were conducted on October 24 2017 with 10 respondents to examine the questions and the time needed to complete them, as well as the cooperation by the respondents. The PMP team was briefed on the result of these interviews

and the interviewers' observations. The first interviewer training was organized on November 2 2017, the second training on November 5 and the final training on November 7. After the completion of the training, corrections were implemented in the questionnaire and additional material based on the interviewers' feedback. The fieldwork was launched on the November 9 2017 and was completed on November 27 2017.

3.3. Interviewer selection and training

The interviewers and coordinators were selected among experienced researchers. All interviewers and coordinators have worked for more than five years in this field, all of whom have bachelor's degrees and more. Most of the interviewers worked with in the PMP pilot survey.

Three training days -7 hours for each- were held to train interviewers and coordinators on the use of questionnaire and accessories. The training was also used to obtain feedback from participants on the questionnaire.

The training was led by Walid Iadadwa from the Jusoor Foundation, whose role was to train researchers to conduct the survey, and Mai Albzour from the local PMP team, whose role was to train researchers and coordinators on the questionnaire and explain the items to them. Sandra Penić from the PMP Lausanne team was also present, and her role was to observe and answer the questions that developed in the training.

As for the timing, number of participants and the venue of the three training days are as follows:

- On November 2nd 2017, the first training was held in the central West Bank area, in the city of Ramallah, which included 10 researchers, a coordinator and two local coordinators. Dr. Randa Nasser also attended this training.
- On November 5th 2017, the second training was held in the southern West Bank area, in the city of Bethlehem, which included 8 researchers, a coordinator and two local coordinators.
- On November 7, 2017, the third training was held in the northern West Bank area, in the city of Nablus, which included 9 researchers, a coordinator and two local coordinators.

The training was also an opportunity to receive feedback from the interviewers on the questionnaire. The items in which we encountered difficulties during the training were the challenging ones, mainly those related to identity in section C, and, less so, questions about vignettes in section E. The interviewers expressed concerns about the length of the questionnaire, and asked to reduce it. Moreover, they expressed concerns about the repetition of some questions such as questions that follow the vignettes and questions related to normalization. The training also led to several discussions between the interviewers and the trainer about the usefulness and justification of some politically sensitive items. Such discussions put the trainer in a sensitive position, where she had to carefully explain the academic purpose behind the items, and justify the Palestinian-Swiss collaboration in a joint research project. Overall, these discussions provided a valuable feedback, and some items were removed and new items developed based on the interviewers' reactions.

3.4. Interviewer supervision and back-checks

Within each field team, a random selection of 5-10% of respondents was contacted again within the work by the regional coordinator. The coordinator closely supervised the work of interviewers throughout the day in the field and conducted the back-checks during the same working day. The coordinator also reviewed at least one interview for each interviewer at the beginning of the fieldwork, to ensure that all the steps were made according to the methodology and to check that interviewers had actually completed the entire interview, and faithfully followed the methodological guidelines. As controls were conducted at the respondents' residence, controllers were in particular able to check whether the addresses of sampling points and contacted households were consistent with the standardized random walk instructions, which left no discretion to the interviewers for the households' selections.

3.5. Interviewer debriefing

After the survey was completed, Mai Albzour and Walid Iadadwa held meetings with researchers in the north, centre and south of West Bank, in order to take feedback on the survey.

Most researchers emphasized the following issues: the length of the questionnaire, the number of different forms, the lack of clarity of some questions such as the section on identity, the

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repetition in the questions following vignettes in section E and the fatigue in the last section F, especially for the items on normalization (F67-79.1). Most of the researchers said that respondents expressed fear while answering questions about the Palestinian Authority and Hamas (items 79 – 93 in section E & items 45 – 47 in section F). Some researchers reported negative attitudes from some participants in relation to the questions on social identity (Section C). These participants expressed desire to end the interview because they showed a lack of interest or understanding why these questions are posed. A few similar positions occurred for some researchers due to the repetition in the questions that followed the vignettes. Some respondents found it difficult to respond on the items regarding the perceived social norms, and particularly problematic was the item whether a narrator would be perceived as a Palestinian patriot (E9, E18, E45, E63, E72)

The only area in which the participants showed high degrees of fear and unwillingness to conduct interviews (such as a full interview in front of the house and not allowing the interviewees to enter) was in Kufr Aqab.

Finally, there was a problem in the items F 130 and 131; which the researchers in the North interpreted differently from the south and the centre. The interviewers gave opposite meanings, which lead to invalid answers.